

Students' Perception on The Use of Picture Series in Writing Procedure Text

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ABSTRACT: The objective of this study is to investigate the students' perception on the use of picture series as a learning media in teaching writing of procedure text. This qualitative design was conducted by using a purposive sampling technique to collect the data. This research involved a class which consisted of 30 students of the tenth grade of a senior high school, Tulang Bawang Barat, Indonesia. The research data were collected by using a close ended questionnaire which measured using five-range Likert scale and analyzed descriptively. The result from this study revealed almost all of the students have positive perceptions when the teacher taught them by using the picture series. The students' positive response reached about 80.80%, compared to the negative response only 2.20% of whole items in the questionnaire, and the rest about 17.00% belonged to the neutral. It is suggested that the using of picture series as a learning media in writing is more interesting and makes them feel easier. The use of pictures can help their difficulty in writing procedure text and encourage their motivation in learning English. Thus, the finding suggests that the English teachers should use this media in teaching writing a procedure paragraph. It is suggested also for the further researcher to explore more the benefits, challenges, and deeper impacts of this media on writing instruction.

KEYWORDS: Learning Media, Perception, Picture Series, Procedure Text, Writing.

INTRODUCTION

English language comprises four primary skills: listening, reading, speaking, and writing. Writing is particularly valuable for enhancing cognitive abilities and thought processes (Jayanti, 2019). Effective written communication allows individuals to articulate their ideas and emotions creatively, making it easier to express themselves verbally. However, many students encounter difficulties in writing, struggling to formulate words, sentences, and paragraphs. A frequent problem is the inability to effectively express ideas in written form. As identified by Wahyuni & Inayati (2020) that a common issue is the difficulty in expressing ideas effectively in written form. Students often lack the ability to develop and organize their thoughts into well-structured paragraphs.

Teaching English, particularly writing, can be challenging due to difficulties in understanding explanations. To bridge this gap, integrating media into instruction is crucial. There are few kinds of instruction media that can be used such as audio, visual and also audiovisual media. In order to resolve this difficulty, the implementation of visual aids, including tangible objects, images, and photographs, will be employed to foster students' writing proficiency. It is supported by Harmer (2007) who emphasizes the value of music and pictures as stimuli for writing and speaking. Pictures offer numerous possibilities for writing activities. Pictures can be awesome and amazing media that can help the teacher to give illustrations in the learning process (Faya, 2020). One of the visual instructional medium that can be employed in this study is the picture series. Picture series have been shown to enhance learners' interest in teaching and learning activities.

Several studies have explored the use of picture series in language learning. Picture series are a compelling instrument to improve students' composing execution (Wilson, 2019). The findings indicate that using picture series can enhance learners' writing skills over time. Gutierrez et al. (2015) conducted action research on using picture series to develop narrative writing among ninth-grade EFL students. Their study revealed that picture series can contribute to the overall improvement of writing skills, particularly in terms of logical sequence and idea generation. Lidyawati and Nirwanto (2016) examined the effectiveness of picture series on students' writing scores. Their research suggests that learners who received instruction using picture series achieved higher scores in writing recount texts compared to those who did not.

In summary, employing picture series as a teaching medium can have a beneficial effect on learning. Nevertheless, research on the perspective of implementation of picture series in learning process, specifically in writing classes is relatively scarce. This study aims to investigate students' perceptions of using picture series in writing classes. Data will be collected through a closed-ended questionnaire administered to 30 first-year high school students.

Additionally, in teaching English writing involves various text genres, including descriptive, narrative, procedural, recount, explanatory, discussion, expository, report, news item, review, and anecdotal texts. While the Merdeka Curriculum for tenth grade focuses on a limited range of genres such as recount, procedure, descriptive, and narrative, this research specifically investigates students' perceptions of using picture series in the context of writing procedural texts. Based on the background, the research question is as follows: What is the student's perception of the implementation of picture series in writing procedure text?

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Writing

English, as a global language, plays a crucial role in our lives. A fundamental English language skill is writing, which enables individuals to express their ideas in written form (Indriani, 2019). Mastering writing is essential for language learning, as it is a key communication tool and a vital skill for academic and professional success. Brown (2001) highlights the process of writing as involving thinking, drafting, and revising. This suggests that effective writing requires careful thought and organization to ensure clear communication of ideas. It implies that in creating a written form, writers should be able to construct their idea perfectly, so the other people can catch the meaning of the message in writing.

Writing is a skill that allows us to express our thoughts and ideas in written form. This skill necessitates specific abilities and cognitive processes, as Selvaraj and Aziz (2019) point out that writing involves organizing ideas within the mind. Consequently, writers must be imaginative and creative in selecting and arranging words to effectively convey meaning to the reader. Atayeva et al. (2019) describe writing as a productive process that involves generating and organizing information into written form. This aligns with Ericsson et al. (2018), who view writing as a cognitive challenge that draws upon memory, reasoning, thinking, and language skills.

While writing is essential for written communication, it is often considered the most challenging of the four language skills due to its complex nature (Richards & Renandya, 2002). The writing process is iterative and requires careful attention to criteria such as organization, content, grammar, vocabulary, and mechanics (Brown, 2004). Pratiwi (2016) supports this view, noting that students often struggle with writing, particularly in areas like organization, content structure, grammar, vocabulary, and mechanics. Consequently, teaching writing, especially for students with limited English proficiency, presents significant challenges and demands careful consideration from English teachers.

In conclusion, writing is a crucial aspect of language learning, particularly English. A solid understanding of writing is essential for effective written and spoken communication.

2.2 Perception

Students' perceptions involve their subjective interpretation of information received through their senses. As noted by Robbins and Judge (2016), perception is the active process where we take the input from our senses (sight, sound, touch, etc.) and arrange it into meaningful patterns that help us comprehend our surroundings. Similarly, Zaiturrahmi et al. (2021) define perspective as a particular way of thinking about or viewing something. Perception plays a vital role in education. Perception is the process of recognizing and making sense of information received through our senses. This includes not only how we interpret this information but also how we react to it. Perception involves taking in sensory data from our surroundings and then using that information to navigate and interact with the world we live in. Perception allows us to transform sensory input into meaningful information. Students' perceptions can vary individually, and positive teacher-student relationships can enhance students' receptiveness to feedback.

Goldstein (2010) explains that the field of perception focuses on understanding how sensory stimulation influences our senses, experiences, and behaviors. Aligned with this theory, the researcher will adapt a previously used questionnaire. This questionnaire focuses on three key indicators: (1) students' attitudes towards using picture series and guided questions, (2) students' experiences with the implementation of the technique, and (3) students' engagement and seriousness in responding to the learning technique. The questionnaire comprises 10 items, with 3 to 4 items for each indicator.

2.3 Learning Media

In effective language teaching, the use of learning media is crucial. Learning media encompass various tools, materials, and resources that support and facilitate the teaching and learning process. These media can stimulate students' thoughts, feelings, attention, and motivation, thereby enhancing the effectiveness and efficiency of learning.

Media serves as a tool for transmitting messages or information from a source to a receiver (Criticos, 1996). By incorporating media into teaching and learning, we can captivate students' attention and interest, making it easier for them to comprehend the material. The primary goal of using learning media is not merely to complete the learning process or attract attention, but to improve the overall quality of teaching and learning (Hikmah, 2019). Additionally, media can save time for both teachers and students by reducing the need for lengthy explanations and allowing for quicker comprehension of the material (Chico & Zrary, 2022).

2.4 Picture Series

Several types of learning media exist, including audio, visual, and audiovisual formats. This study focuses on the use of visual media, which encompass teaching aids relying on visual communication channels. The effectiveness of visual media simulations in enhancing learning outcomes is well-established, with students demonstrating improved retention and understanding (Nurul Jannah in Laraswati, 2016). Research by Laraswati and Suhartono (2016) suggests that using visual media in writing instruction facilitates student writing by stimulating creativity in idea generation and vocabulary development.

Building on these insights, the researcher emphasizes the significance of learning media in the teaching and learning process. This study utilizes picture series, a type of visual media comprised of sequential images that illustrate events, processes, or stories. Picture series hold promise as an engaging medium for writing instruction, as they encourage students to generate ideas for writing (Fitri et al., 2022). Supporting this notion, Romadlona and Khofshoh's (2023) research concludes that picture series media can effectively improve students' real-world writing skills.

2.5 Procedure Text

A procedure text is a type of writing that explains how to complete a particular task or create something. It presents a series of steps or instructions in a sequential order. Procedure texts are commonly found in wide range of contexts such as manuals, recipes, and scientific experiments. Their primary function is to provide clear, sequential instructions to guide individuals through specific processes. According to the explanation above, the researcher conducted the research in teaching procedure text for the first grade students of Senior High School which focused on recipes contexts.

There are three generic structures of procedure text as follows:

a. Goal/Aim

The goal is like the starting line in a race for a procedure text. It tells the readers exactly what we are trying to do before we even start following the steps. It's like the reason for doing the whole thing. For example, in a recipe, the goal might be to bake a delicious chocolate cake. In a science experiment, the goal could be to see how something reacts when we mix certain things together. Knowing the goal helps us understand why we're doing each step and keeps being focused on what we're trying to achieve.

b. Ingredients/ Materials

The materials/ingredients section is like a checklist for success. It provides a complete list of everything you'll need to complete the task, ensuring you have everything readily available before you begin.

- **Materials:** This includes tools, equipment, and other supplies necessary for the task. Think of things like a blender, a knife, a frying pan, or any other tools you might need.
- **Ingredients:** In the context of cooking, this refers to all the specific food items and their quantities needed to prepare a dish. It's essentially a shopping list for your recipe, ensuring you have all the necessary ingredients on hand to start cooking.

By having a clear understanding of the required materials and ingredients, we can prepare efficiently and avoid any frustrating delays or interruptions that might occur if we realize we're missing something crucial in the middle of the process. This section is crucial for smooth and successful task completion.

c. Steps

The steps section is the most important part of the procedure text. It gives the readers a detailed guide on how to do something, with each step clearly and simply explained. The instructions are usually in the form of commands, like "Mix" or "Pour," making it easy

to understand what to do next. It's important that the instructions are easy to follow and don't have any confusing parts, so the readers can easily understand what the writer writes.

RESEARCH METHOD

3.1 Design

This research aimed to display detailed data and information, so a technique of qualitative research was used. This study used a qualitative research approach to gather in-depth information about a specific phenomenon among high school students. The qualitative research focuses on understanding people's attitudes, experiences and behaviors through observation and detailed descriptions..

Participant

This research was conducted in one of Senior High School in Tulang Bawang Barat Regency of Lampung Province. SMAN 3 Tulang Bawang Tengah was selected by the researcher to conduct the research. The population of the research was all of the students in SMAN 3 Tulang Bawang Tengah on the first grade . The population consists of 113 students within 5 classes. By using purposive samplin technique, the researcher took 1 classroom which consists of 30 students as the sample of the research.

3.2 Instrument

This research used a questionnaire to obtain data. The questionnaire was used to find out the students' perceptions after the students who were taught writing by using picture series. The questionnare was administered at the end of the meeting in teaching writing of procedure text by using picture series as the media. The questionnaire was based on theory of Goldstein (2010) who explains that the field of perception concerns explaining the operation of the senses, experiences, and behaviors resulting from the stimulation of the senses. It was a close-ended questionnaire that consists of 10 statements. Likert- Scales-based questionnaire was used in this research, the scale had the following categorical terms: (1) strongly disagree, (2) diagree, (3) neutral, (4) agree, (5) strongly agree. The questionnaire was distributed to the students in two languages; in English and also translated in Bahasa Indonesia to make them easier in filling it. The instrument used in this research is described as follows:

Questionnaire: The questionnaire was adapted from Pirka et al. (2024) to find out students' opinions after learning writing by using the medium of picture series

Table 1. List of Questionnaire Items

No	Indicator/ Statements	1	2	3	4	5
Students' English Attitude						
1	I think learn English by using picture series is interesting <i>(Saya merasa belajar Bahasa Inggris menggunakan picture series itu menarik)</i>					
2	I think learning writing by using picture series is easier <i>(Saya merasa belajar menulis menggunakan picture series itu lebih mudah)</i>					
3	I am very happy to join this English Class <i>(Saya sangat senang mengikuti kelas Bahasa Inggris ini)</i>					
Students' Experiences		1	2	3	4	5
4	I get good experience during the teaching-learning process. <i>(Saya mendapatkan pengalaman yang baik selama proses belajar mengajar)</i>					
5	I can organize my idea to write a procedure text easily using picture series <i>(Saya bisa mengembangkan ide-ide saya untuk menulis teks prosedur dengan mudah menggunakan picture series)</i>					

6	I always pay attention to the teacher’s explanation when delivering material <i>(Saya selalu memperhatikan penjelasan guru ketika menyampaikan materi)</i>					
7	I can write step by step, identifying the goal, ingredients and steps in making something <i>(Saya bisa menulis langkah demi langkah, mengidentifikasi tujuan, bahan-bahan dan langkah-langkah dalam membuat sesuatu)</i>					
Students’ Behavior		1	2	3	4	5
8	I always follow the instructions given by the teacher. <i>(Saya selalu mengikuti perintah yang diberikan oleh guru)</i>					
9	I am able to compose sentence in form of grammatical correct <i>(Saya dapat membuat kalimat dengan susunan kalimat yang benar)</i>					
10	I am encouraged to do my best to create procedure text <i>(Saya terdorong untuk melakukan yang terbaik untuk membuat teks procedure)</i>					

3.3 Data collecting technique

In conducting the research, the researchers used questionnaire consisting of close-ended questions. The questionnaire Adapted from Pirka, et al. (2024) which three aspects were elaborated in the questionnaire: English attitude (student’s perspective on the use of picture series), Experiences (what students get of the implementation of technique), and Behavior (how is the seriousness of students in responding to learning technique). The questionnaire consists of 10 items, with 3 to 4 items in each indicator. They can be seen in the following list:

- a. Question number 1-3 deal with English attitude (student’s perspective on the use of picture series).
- b. Question number 4-7 deal with Experiences (what students get from the implementation of the technique).
- c. Question number 8-10 deal with Behavior (how is the seriousness of students in responding to learning technique).

The questionnaire items were organized in easy and short language to ask the children so that they could be answered dynamically. Therefore, the questions were structured and consistent. The questionnaire was given directly after the students finished the writing learning by using picture series. Next, the researcher inputs all of the students’ response and calculate the score of each item of the questionnaire. Lastly, the researcher percentaged each calculation in order to have a deeper analysis.

3.4 Data analysis

To answer the aim of the research about students’ perception after the students were taught by using picture series, the researcher calculated the responses and total all points of each student by using a Likert scale. Then, the data were analyzed by using descriptive statistic analysis. The scales in the questionnaire were converted into numerical values as the table shown below:

Table 2: Interpretation of Mean Score

No.	Mean Score	Interpretation
1	1.00 – 1.80	Very low
2	1.81 – 2.60	Low
3	2.61 – 3.40	Medium
4	3.41 – 4.20	High
5	4.21 – 5.00	Very high

RESULT

The questionnaire consists of 10 questions that students must answer. It used the Likert scale type with 5 choices of strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree, and strongly disagree. The questionnaire consists of 10 items, with 3 to 4 items in each indicator. In this research, three main indicators were examined in this study. In this research, items 1 to 3 are about English attitude (student’s perspective on the use of picture series). Items 4 to 7 are about experiences (what students get of the implementation of technique). Items 8 to 10 are about behavior (how is the seriousness of students in responding to learning technique). The questionnaire was distributed to the students in two languages, in English and also in Bahasa Indonesia to make them easier and get the real data. The result of students’ responses for the questionnaire can be seen in the following table:

Table 3: Result of questionnaire

No	Statements	Frequency of answer					Mean	SD	Level of Interpretation
		1	2	3	4	5			
1	I think learn English by using picture series is interesting	0 0 %	0 0 %	6 20%	15 50%	9 30%	4.10	0.712	High
2	I think learning writing by using picture series is easier	0 0 %	2 7%	7 23 %	14 47%	7 23%	3.87	0.860	High
3	I am very happy to join this English Class	0 0%	0 0%	4 13%	11 37%	15 50 %	4.37	0.718	Very High
4	I get good experience during the teaching-learning process.	0 0 %	1 3%	2 7%	15 50 %	12 40 %	4.27	0.740	Very High
5	I can organise my idea to write a procedure text about favorite food and drink easily using picture series.	0 0%	1 3%	6 20%	12 40 %	11 37%	4.07	0.868	High
6	I always pay attention to the teacher’s explanation when delivering material	0 0 %	0 0 %	2 7%	12 40 %	16 53 %	4.47	0.629	Very High
7	I can write step by step, identifying the goal, ingredients and steps in making something.	0 0 %	1 3%	6 20%	12 40 %	11 37 %	4.10	0.845	High
8	I always follow the instructions given by the teacher.	0 0 %	1 3%	3 10 %	11 37%	15 50 %	4.33	0.802	Very High
9	I am able to compose sentence in form of grammatical correct.	0 0%	0 0 %	9 30 %	13 43 %	8 27 %	3.97	0.765	High
10	I am encouraged to do my best to create procedure text.	0 0 %	1 3%	6 20 %	8 27 %	15 50 %	4.23	0.898	Very High

The data presented in the table reflects students' perceptions of learning English through picture series. Overall, the responses indicate a **positive perception** towards this teaching technique. For instance, when asked if learning English using picture series is interesting, **80% of students rated it on 4 or 5**, suggesting that they agree even very agree that this technique is engaging. This high level of interest may be caused of pictures as visual media that help in comprehension and retention, making the learning

experience more enjoyable and effective. In terms of ease of learning, the responses to the statement about writing using picture series with guided questions show a **similar percentage**. Furthermore, **70% of students rated their experience on scale 4 or 5**, indicating that they agree this technique is easier for writing tasks. This suggests that the using of visual media may facilitate better organization of thoughts and ideas, which is crucial in writing. The positive feedback on writing skills could also imply that students feel more confident in their abilities when using this media, which can lead to improved academic performance. Moreover, the data also highlights students' overall satisfaction with the English class. A significant **87% of students expressed happiness** in participating in the class, with many feeling they gained valuable experiences during the learning process. Such findings underscore the effectiveness of using picture series as a effective teaching technique in writing, promoting not only engagement but also skill development in language learning.

The deeper analysis of all aspects are discussed in the following elaboration:

1. **English attitude (student’s perspective on the use of picture series)**

The pie chart illustrates the mean scores for three items related to English language attitude perception. Each slice of the pie represents one item, and the size of the slice corresponds to the mean score. The diagram shows a positive attitude towards English learning using picture series and joining English classes. The mean scores for all three items are above 3.87, indicating a favorable perception.

1. **Item 1:** With a mean score of 4.10, this item shows a high level of positive attitude. It suggested that participants generally found learning English through this method engaging. However, it is slightly lower than Item 3, suggesting a slightly less favorable view compared to Item 3.
2. **Item 2:** This item has the lowest mean score of 3.87. While still indicating a positive attitude, it suggests a slightly less favorable view compared to the other two items. This could indicate that while participants appreciated the visual aid, they may have perceived some challenges in applying it to writing tasks.
3. **Item 3:** This item has the highest mean score of 4.37, indicating the strongest positive attitude among the three items. This suggests that the respondents hold a very favorable view towards this particular aspect of English language learning. It demonstrated a strong positive sentiment towards participating in the English class.

2. **Experiences (what students get from the implementation of the technique)**

The pie chart illustrates the mean scores for four items related to experiences perception. Each slice of the pie represents one item, and the size of the slice corresponds to the mean score. The diagram shows a positive perception of the teaching-learning process, with students indicating they have had good experiences and can effectively organize their ideas and write procedure texts.

1. **Item 4:** With a mean score of 4.27, this item shows a high level of positive perception. It suggested that students generally found the teaching-learning process to be positive and beneficial
2. **Item 5:** This item has the lowest mean score of 4.07. While still indicating a positive perception, it suggests a slightly less favorable view compared to the other three items. This could indicate that while students found the picture series helpful, some may have encountered challenges in organizing their ideas for writing procedure texts.
3. **Item 6:** This item has the highest mean score of 4.47, indicating the most positive perception among the four items. Demonstrating a strong commitment to active listening and engagement during the teacher's explanations.
4. **Item 7:** This item has a mean score of 4.10, indicating that students were generally able to structure their writing to include the key elements of a procedure text.

3. Behavior (the seriousness of students in responding to the learning technique)

The pie chart illustrates the mean scores for three items related to students' behavior perception. Each slice of the pie represents one item, and the size of the slice corresponds to the mean score. The diagram shows a positive perception of students' behavior, with a strong emphasis on following instructions and encouragement to do their best.

1. **Item 8:** This item has the highest mean score of 4.33, indicating that students generally adhere to the teacher's instructions.
2. **Item 9:** This item has the lowest mean score of 3.97. This could indicate that while students are generally able to compose sentences, some may require additional support or practice in ensuring grammatical accuracy.
3. **Item 10:** With a mean score of 4.23, suggesting that students feel motivated to put effort into writing procedure texts.

From all the students' answers to 10 items in the questionnaire, it can be concluded that the students have a positive perception in the using of picture series in writing procedural text. It can be seen from the data that the most of the students agree on these questionnaire items. Nevertheless, some students disagree with the items in the perception questionnaire. The students said that they did not have no much time in making English written text, because they work individually in composing the text. There was a group work only in the second meeting after pretest, in the next day they have to do the task and write procedure text individually. Unclear picture From all the findings and it's discussions, it can be stated that the use of picture series can have a positive effect on students' writing and also can build students to have a good perception about those techniques in teaching writing.

DISCUSSIONS

The discussion of research findings in each indicator can be elaborated as follows:

1. English attitude (student's perspective on the use of picture series)

The high scores for Items 1 and 2 indicate that participants found the use of picture series to be a valuable tool for learning English, particularly for making the learning process more engaging and potentially easier. The high score for Item 3 suggests that

participants were generally satisfied with the English class and were motivated to learn. The slightly lower score for Item 2 might indicate that participants required more guidance or practice in applying the picture series method to writing tasks.

Based on items 1 to 3 about English attitude, it can be concluded that the students also have a strong preference for their teacher and enjoy the lesson. This indicates a favorable outlook on the learning environment and materials. However, further investigation may be needed to understand the reasons for neutrality or disagreement among some students.

2. Experiences (what students get from the implementation of technique)

The high scores for Items 4 and 7 suggest that students perceive the teaching-learning process to be engaging and conducive to learning. The positive score for Item 5 indicates that the picture series method can be a valuable tool for helping students organize their ideas for writing procedure texts. The slightly lower score for Item 5 might indicate that some students require additional support or practice in organizing their thoughts and applying the picture series method to writing tasks.

From the responses of questions number 4 to 7 about students' experiences in implementing picture series, it can be concluded that the majority of students had positive experiences during the teaching-learning process, as well as with the use of the integrated picture series in contributing organizing ideas in writing. However, there is a noticeable percentage of students who were neutral or disagreed that the pictures gave them the background knowledge to build their ideas. This may indicate a need for further exploration into the effectiveness of using pictures as a tool to develop ideas in the learning process.

3. Behavior (the seriousness of students in responding to learning technique)

The high score for Item 8 suggests a positive classroom environment where students are receptive to the teacher's guidance. The slightly lower score for Item 9 highlights the importance of ongoing support and practice in developing grammatical accuracy in students' writing. The positive score for Item 10 indicates that the learning environment encourages students to strive for their best in their writing tasks.

Based on the responses in items 8 to 10 about behavior, the majority of students appear to be actively engaged in their English learning. They generally pay attention to the teacher's explanations and follow instructions. Additionally, a significant percentage of students feel encouraged to do their best when creating procedure texts based on pictures. However, there is a lower percentage of students who feel confident in composing grammatically correct sentences based on pictures, indicating a potential area for improvement or further support in this aspect of learning.

Based on findings, From 10 items of questions in the questionnaire, students who answered positively in the experimental group reached about 80.80%, compared to the negative response which students gave only 2.20% of whole items in the questionnaire, and the rest about 17.00% belonged to the neutral. It indicates that the students agree that picture series can affect their learning process positively. The data results indicate that the students have a positive perception of the techniques used in writing. It happens because the students felt enjoyable during the class, they could elaborate their ideas before writing through stages provided in the integrated picture series with guided questions. The data also generally indicates high levels of agreement among respondents on most statements. This suggests that the use of picture series in teaching English, particularly writing, was perceived positively by the participants. Moreover, it is supported by the statement from Erniwati et al. (2019) who state that picture series is appropriately selected, it can lead to the enthusiasm and a lively learning atmosphere. Consequently, the teaching and learning processes are effective. It is also supported by the statement from Agustyawaty et al. (2021) who state Pictures can motivate students and make them want to pay attention to take a part in class and also contribute their idea to the context in which the language is being used in class. it can be concluded that the majority of students have positive perceptions towards English and they are enthusiastic about their English class.

CONCLUSION

5.1 Conclusion

The research question of this study focused on students' perception of the implementation of picture series in the writing procedural text. While previous studies primarily focused on the effects of using picture series media in the learning process, this research focused on the students' perception about students' perspective on the use of picture series, what students get of the implementation of picture series, and how is the seriousness of students in responding to learning technique in writing classrooms. This topic is still

relatively rare to be discussed in Indonesia. So, the researcher tried to conduct this study to get deeper data about the students' perception of the implementation of picture series media in the writing classroom. The researcher had displayed how the students' perceptions of the picture series media were good in the writing classroom. The result of the study also showed that students like and enjoy the media in the writing classroom. All the participants who had completed the questionnaire realized that the activity had benefited significantly.

5.2 Suggestions

This research found that using picture series in writing classes can be challenging. Students struggled due to limited time for group discussions and unclear pictures. This made the lessons feel rushed. As a result, It implies that teachers need to continue and develop this media in writing class as it gives students' benefit in communicating, creating, teamwork, and creativity. To optimize their use, teachers can allocate more time for group discussions: This will allow for deeper understanding and idea development. Teachers also should ensure picture clarity: Check and revise pictures to avoid visual obstacles. This study uncovered new insights into the difficulties of using picture series, which can inform future research. Further investigation is needed to explore the benefits, challenges, and deeper impacts of this media on writing instruction.

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